

STROBE Statement—Checklist of items that should be included in reports of cohort studies

Item No.	Recommendation	Reported on page/section
	Title and Abstract	
1 (a)	Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	Title / Abstract: 1,2
1 (b)	Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	Abstract: 2
	Introduction	
2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Introduction: 4
3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Introduction: 4
	Methods	
4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Methods – Study setting: 5
5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Methods – Study setting: 5
6 (a)	Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants. Describe methods of follow-up	Methods – Sample selection: 5
6 (b)	For matched studies, give matching criteria and number of exposed and unexposed	Not applicable
7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Methods – Variables: 7
8	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if more than one group	Methods – Staining procedures & Evaluation: 6

9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Methods – Evaluation: 6,7
10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	Methods – Sample selection: 5,6
11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	Methods – Statistical analysis: 7
12 (a)	Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	Methods – Statistical analysis: 7
12 (b)	Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	Not applicable
12 (c)	Explain how missing data were addressed	Methods – Sample selection (exclusions): 5,6
12 (d)	If applicable, explain how loss to follow-up was addressed	Not applicable
12 (e)	Describe any sensitivity analyses	Methods – ROC/AUC interpretation: 7
	Results	
13 (a)	Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study (e.g., numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed)	Results – Sample selection: 5,6
13 (b)	Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	Methods – Sample selection (exclusions): 5, 6
13 (c)	Consider use of a flow diagram	Not applicable
14 (a)	Give characteristics of study participants (e.g., demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	Results – Descriptive data: 8, 9
14 (b)	Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	Not applicable (excluded during selection)
15	Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures over time	Results – H. pylori detection outcomes: 11

16 (a)	Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (e.g., 95% CI). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why	Results – Diagnostic performance (sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, AUC): 12
16 (b)	Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	Not applicable
16 (c)	If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	Not applicable
17	Report other analyses done (e.g., subgroup analyses and interactions, sensitivity analyses)	Results – ROC curve comparisons: 13
	Discussion	
18	Summarize key results with reference to study objectives	Discussion – Key findings: 15-19
19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	Discussion – Limitations: 19
20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Discussion – Interpretation: 15-19
21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Discussion – Generalisability: 19
	Other Information	
22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	Funding: 21